

MusicFone Task

General Description:

MusicFone is a music playing application that runs on a GPS-enabled and MP3-capable mobile-phone. MusicFone application will make recommendations for artists, the AppUser may like to listen depending upon his listening habits. And, the app finds upcoming events for these artists using data gathered from Last.Fm website. The following functions will enable MusicFone to make recommendations and plan a travel itinerary to concert events.

F1: Recommend Artists:

MusicFone application recommends 20 artists based on the currently played artist on the application by the AppUser. These recommended artists are the 20 most-frequently-appearing artists among the LastFm Users who are also the top/highest fans of the currently played artist by the AppUser. MusicFone application also displays the fan-count of the recommended artists - next to their names - based on the fan-following count from Last.Fm website.

F2: Finding Concerts for an Artist:

When a MusicFone user (AppUser) clicks an artist from a list of recommended artists then a list of destinations of the upcoming concerts of that artist is displayed to him – based on the data from Last.FM website. Each destination contains information on the upcoming concert (location, day, date and time) together with the distance to the concerts' location from the AppUser's current GPS location.

F3: Itinerary for Concerts:

The AppUser can select an artist from the list of recommended artists by adding an artist to the list of selected artists who the AppUser would like to attend the concert of. The application then adds the concert of the artist to the trip itinerary section based on the location close to the AppUser's current location. Similarly the AppUser can remove the artists from the selected artists' list and even clear all of his selections. When the selected artists' list is changed based on the AppUsers' actions, the application displays a recalculated itinerary to the AppUser. An itinerary is a list of Destinations, where each destination contains the artist's name, concert's information (location, day, date, time), and the distance from the previous Destination. However, the first Destination shows distance from the AppUser's current location. The itinerary must be chronologically ordered according to the start-date of the concerts in it. The itinerary should satisfy the following constraints:

1. The itinerary starts with the concert having the earliest start-date for any of the selected artists.
2. An artist has at most one concert in the itinerary (some artists may have no concerts, however).
3. No two concerts in the itinerary may take place on the same day.
4. If multiple artists have concerts on the same day, the itinerary includes only the concert that is closest in distance to the previous Destination.
5. If the same artist has multiple concerts on the same day, the itinerary includes only the concert that is closest in distance to the previous Destination.